

The communication format *Science & Cinema*: reflecting on representations of science in movies for joint meaning-making

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ABSTRACT: We present ‘Science & Cinema, a science communication format combining a cinematic atmosphere with scientific expertise. By examining clips from various movies, the format encourages the audience to critically reflect on representations of scientific topics in our popular culture. The evaluation of pre- and post-event questionnaires, along with a focus group session, revealed that the format appeals to different target groups, entertains, creates interest, and fosters understanding and reflection. By making images explicit, the format shows potential to contribute to the understanding and meaning-making of scientific topics that are strongly present in social discourses.

Keywords: Science and Cinema; film; audience; fiction; reflection; public understanding of science

Introduction

In this practice-insight, we present ‘*Science & Cinema (S&C)*’ for the first time – an innovative science communication format that uses the powerful visual language of movies to transport the audience into popular conceptions of science and scientific topics. The screening of film clips sets the stage for a scientist who analyzes the transported images and examines the conformities and divergences with established scientific facts and research. This format aims (1) to attract people’s attention towards science, (2) to provide deeper insights into the respective scientific field, and (3) to engage the audience in a critical reflection on the representation of science and scientific topics in movies. Here, we present the episode ‘*Science & Cinema: Climate, Collapse, Catastrophes*’ as an example for the implementation of the format for the topic of climate change. We report on the results of the concept evaluation and conclude with practical recommendations for designing future science communication events.

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36 *The 'science communication as culture' framework*

37 Recently, broader conceptions of science communication have been proposed: Bucchi
38 and Trench (2021, p. 6) define science communication as “the social conversation
39 around science,” also recognizing images and ideas related to science in popular
40 culture. Instead of limiting science communication by strict strategic and prescriptive
41 notions, they acknowledge the diversity of formats and practices and suggest thinking
42 of science communication as “encouraging the public to think about, respond to and
43 discuss science and its role in society” (Bucchi & Trench 2021, p. 5).

44
45 In a similar vein, Davies and colleagues (Davies et al., 2019; Horst & Davies, 2021)
46 argue for conceptualizing science communication as cultural in nature. They consider
47 science communication as part of the public communication about science and
48 therefore propose that focusing on the meaning created by public stories can help
49 guide science communication practice and research. This cultural approach seems to
50 be particularly helpful when it comes to frequently debated topics in society, such as
51 climate change.

52
53 It has been argued that climate change is an especially challenging topic for
54 communication: it is abstract in nature, which facilitates psychological distance to the
55 topic (Spence et. al, 2012); political polarization and emotional debates raise
56 skepticism (Hahnel et al., 2020); misinformation strengthens existing misconceptions
57 (Treen et al., 2020), and lay people’s knowledge about the topic is often limited and
58 characterized by multiple misunderstandings (Fischer et al., 2019; Thaller &
59 Brudermann, 2020). In light of these challenges, there is a clear need for engaging
60 communication formats that recognize the role of conversations around science in
61 meaning-making.

62
63 The representations of scientific topics in popular culture influence our individual
64 perceptions and shared conceptions about science (Bucchi & Trench, 2021; Davies et
65 al., 2019). Studies have shown that climate-fiction films draw attention to climate
66 change, shaping our understanding and emotional responses through dystopian
67 visions (e.g., Hart & Leiserowitz, 2009; Lowe et al., 2006; Sakellari, 2015). When
68 developing a science communication strategy, it may be useful to actively account for
69 these science-related cultural definitions, depictions, and stories present in our society
70 (Horst & Davies, 2021; Sakellari, 2015).

71 **Science & Cinema (S&C)**

72 We designed the S&C format to attract people’s attention for science using the
73 engaging power of movies. In the landscape of science-audiovisual engagement,
74 formats differ in terms of film genres and involvement of experts and audiences. Sci-fi
75 nights are screenings of fictional mainstream films focusing on entertainment, whereas
76 cinema debates take up documentary films and include reflective discussions with
77 experts and the audience. Science film festivals and sci-art exhibitions mostly show
78 independent short films covering documentaries to artistic fiction. Film festivals mostly

79 are structured events with varying degrees of expert and audience involvement, while
80 exhibitions are usually discovered individually.

81

82 S&C takes its own place within this landscape showing clips from multiple movies. S&C
83 episodes last around 90 minutes and are organized into five narrative blocks. Each
84 block consists of a screening of thematically curated and compiled film clips followed
85 by a moderated discussion. In our episodes, we invite a scientist from our university,
86 but other experts in the respective field (scientists, science communicators, science
87 journalists) could take on the role of discussion participant. The alternation of
88 screenings of 5-10 minutes with discussion not only provides clear structure, it aims at
89 stimulating the audience's attention. Clip selection allows a focused, yet emotional,
90 exploration of the cinematic representation of the scientific topic and its evolution in
91 movies over time. Whereas full-length films may be stronger in mentally absorbing
92 people into the story (narrative transportation) and in identification with characters, they
93 may distract the audience from the topic at hand (Griffin, 2017). Documentaries better
94 represent the nature of science; independent films are characterized by realism and
95 challenging classical cinematic tropes (Felgueiras & Ruão, 2025). S&C, however, uses
96 movies to integrate precisely these cultural images that they convey. The moderator-
97 scientist dialogue adds the scientific view on the topics and reflects how the images
98 may support or distort our perception of science. The participating expert analyzes the
99 clips for their degree of realism, corrects factual misrepresentations, clarifies potential
100 misunderstandings, and contextualizes the information based on current scientific
101 knowledge. In the end, the audience is invited to join the discussion. The S&C format
102 is suitable for various disciplines, as long as the topic has been addressed in movies
103 over time. We have created various episodes covering topics of natural sciences and
104 humanities, e.g., for microbiology ('Zombies, monsters and mutants in science and
105 film') or medieval research ('Mongols, monks, minstrelsy: What medieval films like
106 Robin Hood and Braveheart reveal').

107 *The episode 'Climate, Collapse, Catastrophes'*

108 We implemented the S&C concept for the topic of climate change in the episode
109 'Climate, Collapse, Catastrophes' (Figure 1). Prominent climate scenarios and their
110 impacts build the five narrative blocks *ice* (into an ice age), *water* (melting poles, sea
111 level rise and floods), *wind and extreme weather events*, *droughts*, and *migration*;
112 covering five of seven main themes taken up in cli-fi films (Svoboda, 2016; excluding
113 preclima(c)tic stress disorder and antagonists which do not focus on impacts). For
114 detailed clip description and filmography see Supplementary File [S1](#). The dense
115 presentation in thematic blocks makes the narratives and transported images explicit.
116 During a moderated discussion, the scientist examines these images and resumes the
117 scientific perspective

118

- 119 • Block 1 (ice): Clips show an ice age caused by the halt of the North Atlantic
120 current due to global warming. The vice-president admits mistakes made in the
121 CO₂ reduction policy (*The Day After Tomorrow*; Emmerich, 2004). This is

122 followed by scenes from *Snowpiercer* (Joon-Ho, 2013), showing an ice-covered
123 city in the USA after a failed scientific Earth-cooling experiment.

124

125 After this screening, the moderator asks the scientist about the physical
126 connection of global warming and ice ages in geological history, and the
127 probability of them reoccurring in the (near) future.

128

129 • Block 2 (water): The squirrel Scrat (*Ice Age*; Saldanha, 2006) causes a dam
130 breach of a meltwater lake. Film sequences from *AI*, *The Day After Tomorrow*,
131 *Waterworld* (Reynolds & Costner, 1995), and *Hard Rain* (Salomon, 1998)
132 alternate, dramatically showing the destructive power of water. *A.I.* (Spielberg,
133 2001) depicts coastal cities worldwide situated meters under water due to
134 melted polar ice caps.

135

136 The scientist outlines the connection between CO₂ emissions and the melting
137 of the polar ice, the possible extent of sea level rise, and its consequences.

138

139 • Block 3 (wind/extreme weather): A tornado sucks a man out of his bunker
140 (*Twister*; De Bont, 1996), followed by images of various extreme weather events
141 (deadly heat waves, droughts, hurricanes and tornadoes, tsunamis) from *The*
142 *Day After Tomorrow*, *Geostorm* (Devlin, 2017), and *Mad Max - Fury Road*
143 (Miller, 2015).

144

145 The scientist explains the F-tornado scale and whether tornadoes can also
146 occur locally. It is discussed how recently experienced severe storms and heavy
147 rainfalls relate to climate change.

148

149 • Block 4 (droughts) starts with a narrative voiceover from *Mad Max 2* (Miller,
150 1981), where the failure of politics led to a post-apocalyptic world, featuring
151 water scarcity and deserts. Scenes from *Soylent Green* (Fleischer, 1973) show
152 a world divided into rich and poor, where corpses are processed into food to
153 overcome shortages.

154

155 The moderator-scientist discussion touches upon desertification and its
156 consequences, food waste as source of CO₂ emissions, and other lifestyle
157 issues like excessive water consumption.

158

159 • Block 5 (migration): In Sudan, a group of refugees start their journey to Europe
160 due to shortages in fuels and crop failures. A young man shoots a pistol into the
161 air out of joy after arriving on the Spanish coast and is then shot by soldiers (all
162 clips from *The March*; Wheatley, 1990).

163

164 Considering that *The March* presented several social challenges related to
165 climate change as early as 1990, the scientist mentions that there was already

166 a lot of scientific knowledge about climate change and possible strategies for
167 action available at that time. He discusses the slow implementation of climate
168 policy in relation to scientific progress. To avoid leaving the audience with
169 feelings of helplessness, the scientist integrates messages in line with the
170 concept of “constructive hope”, like thinking about ways to reach a desired goal
171 (pathway thinking; “Let's take freight transport as an example: transport costs
172 can be adjusted so that the absurd back-and-forth transport of goods across
173 Europe is no longer economically viable.”) or to strive to actively reach these
174 goals (agency seeking; “We have shown as humanity that we can solve
175 problems if we really recognize them, like the problem with the hole in the ozone
176 layer.”) (Ojala, 2023).

Setup	Excerpts from the films as examples of the dramatic realization	Depictions of climate change/science in clips
<p>Block 1: ice</p>	<p>1a.) NASA satellite image: thunderstorm cells cool the northern hemisphere in just a few days. <i>The Day After Tomorrow</i> (Roland Emmerich, 2004) 00:04:59. 1b.) The northern hemisphere under a permanent ice sheet. <i>The Day After Tomorrow</i> (Roland Emmerich, 2004) 00:05:25.</p> <p>moderated reflection with the scientist</p>	<p>Melting of poles leading to extreme weather events and continent-spanning storms bringing a new ice age to the northern hemisphere. Trope: heroic scientist unheard by politicians (<i>The Day After Tomorrow</i>)</p>
<p>Block 2: water</p>	<p>1c.) The three animal friends realize that their habitat is changing fundamentally. <i>Ice Age – The meltdown</i> (Carlos Saldanha, 2006) 00:02:15. 1d.) New York City is flooded by a tidal wave. <i>The Day After Tomorrow</i> (Roland Emmerich, 2004) 00:01:21</p> <p>moderated reflection with the scientist</p>	<p>Melting in the end of historical ice age (<i>Ice Age – the Meltdown</i>); Melting of poles leading to floods and inundation of coastal cities (<i>Water World, Hard Rain, The Day After Tomorrow, A.I.</i>), forcing to migration (<i>A.I.</i>).</p>
<p>Block 3: wind / extreme weather</p>	<p>1e.) Dubai is hit by a tidal wave triggered by a satellite. <i>Geostorm</i> (Dean Devlin, 2017) 00:02:23 1f.) Climate change is causing three hurricanes to hit Los Angeles at the same time. <i>The Day After Tomorrow</i> (Roland Emmerich, 2004) 00:05:06.</p> <p>moderated reflection with the scientist</p>	<p>Destroying tornadoes and hurricanes (<i>Twister, The Day After Tomorrow, Mad Max – Fury Road</i>); Deadly heatwave and hailstorm (<i>Geostorm</i>); Trope: humanity attempts technical solution and fails (<i>Geostorm</i>)</p>
<p>Block 4: droughts</p>	<p>1g.) New York's last tree is housed in a shelter tent. <i>Soylent Green</i> (Richard Fleischer, 1973) 00:05:50. 1h.) The corpses are processed into food in a factory. <i>Soylent Green</i> (Richard Fleischer, 1973) 00:07:49 .</p> <p>moderated reflection with the scientist</p>	<p>Desertification and hostile living conditions, water scarcity and famine (clips from <i>Mad Max</i> film series; <i>Soylent Green</i>); Living conditions: everyday things like meat, showers or paper become precious (<i>Snowpiercer, Waterworld, Soylent Green</i>)</p>
<p>Block 5: migra- tion</p>	<p>1i.) Migrants wait for safe passage from Morocco to Spain. <i>The March</i> (David Wheatley, 1990) 00:14:15. 1j.) Migrants jump out of boats with joy as they arrive on the coast of Spain. <i>The March</i> (David Wheatley, 1990) 00:15:44 .</p> <p>moderated reflection with the scientist</p>	<p>Climate change migration due to hostile living conditions; Europeans want to be “good people”, but at the same time they don't want to restrict themselves; the people affected should remain in their home countries (<i>The March</i>)</p>

Figure 1: Concept of the science communication event ‘Science & Cinema: Climate, Collapse, Catastrophes’ with impressions of the images used in movies.

180 **Objectives**

181 We evaluate the S&C format with regards to five questions: (1) which kind of audience
182 participates; (2) which impact does the venue have on the composition of the audience;
183 (3) what does the audience expect; (4) how do they perceive the event in terms of
184 entertainment, sparking interest, and scientific information; and (5) what are the
185 motivations and goals of the scientist engaged in the S&C? The intended outcome of
186 the event is to inspire critical reflection on scientific topics and their representations in
187 movies. As an indicator for initiated reflection, we examined how the event influenced
188 the audiences' attitudes toward climate change regarding concern, risk perception, and
189 motivation.

190 **Methods**

191 The S&C event was held twice: once in a university lecture hall that was open to the
192 public and once in a cinema as part of a local film festival (see Figure 2).

193
194 We evaluated the S&C format as follows (1) a quantitative evaluation with pre-/post-
195 event online questionnaires with the audiences, (2) a qualitative evaluation through a
196 focus group after the event, and (3) a short, written interview with the participating
197 scientist.
198

199
200 **Figure 2:** Impressions of the two S&C: *Climate, Collapse, Catastrophes* events taking place in a
201 university lecture hall (1st row) and in a cinema as part of the 'Science meets Fiction Festival' (2nd row).

202
203 *Pre-/post-event study*

204 For data collection, participants completed the questionnaires online (Supplementary
205 File [S2](#)). We gathered 62 complete questionnaires at the university and 33 at the

206 cinema. The pre-event questionnaire captured participation motives, expectations,
207 current knowledge, and demographics. The post-event questionnaire gathered
208 feedback on the event, including whether expectations were met in terms of
209 entertainment, interest, and scientific information. In order to assess the format's
210 potential to initiate reflection, participants were asked to which degree they had
211 changed their view on climate change in terms of understanding, knowledge, risk
212 perception, concern, and intention to act. The questionnaires are partially based on
213 van der Linden's climate perception instrument (2015) and were adapted to our study's
214 queries. The descriptive and quantitative data analysis was carried out in R.

215 *Focus group session*

216 To gain deeper insights and descriptive information about how the event was
217 perceived, participants were invited to take part in a focus group, which was only
218 realized after the university event due to organizational constraints. It was held three
219 days after the event (see Supplementary File [S3](#) for the interview guide). Five people
220 participated, all between the ages of 24 and 34: four from a master's program, one
221 university graduate. Statements and conclusions are therefore based on a small and
222 homogenous sample. The interview lasted 100 minutes. For qualitative content
223 analysis, the interview was transcribed and coded in MAXQDA2022 (for the transcript
224 and detailed results, see Supplementary Files [S4](#) and [S5](#)).

225 **Results**

226 *The S&C audience*

227 We observed differences between the two audiences. Participants were younger at
228 university: 65% (n=40) were between 18 and 27 years old, whereas at the cinema,
229 60% (n=20) were between 28 and 45 (all data tables are available in Supplementary
230 File [S6](#)). Participants were balanced according to gender (university: 53%; cinema:
231 52% women).

232
233 Regarding education level, at the university, 39% indicated A-levels, 32% bachelor's
234 degrees and 23% master's degrees, 3% indicated a PhD, one compulsory school
235 (<1%). At the cinema, we observed higher values in the marginal categories with 12%
236 indicating compulsory school, and 15% holding a PhD. Also here, most participants
237 held A-levels (21%), bachelor's (18%) or master's degree (33%). We see clear
238 differences for the audiences' affiliation with university (see Figure 3): whereas the
239 majority of the participants at university (77%) indicated close affiliation via their study
240 or work, 73% of the people visiting the cinema event had no affiliation with university.

241

242

243

Figure 3: Audiences' affiliation with the university differentiated for the two venues.

244 In both groups, participants often think about climate change (university: 85%, cinema:
 245 75%) and express high concern (rating ≥ 5 on a 7-point-Likert scale; university: 92%,
 246 cinema: 87%). In the pretest, the majority indicated high motivation to personally
 247 engage against climate change (rating ≥ 5 ; university: 85%, cinema: 63%). However,
 248 for the cinema setting, almost one third expressed rather low motivation (30% rated 2
 249 or 3).

250 *Perception of the S&C event*

251 Participants mainly found out about the event via personal contacts (university: 66%,
 252 cinema: 55%) and for the cinema via poster advertising (27%). Social media,
 253 newsletters, and websites played minor roles (< 10%).

254

255 Participants expected primarily information (university: 89%, cinema: 88%) and
 256 entertainment (university: 74%, cinema: 58%). Insights into research results
 257 (university: 48%, cinema: 52%) and suggestions for climate action (university: 35%,
 258 cinema: 39%) were expected at lower rates.

259 Entertainment and interest

260 Most people in the audience generally liked the event (mean value for the university
 261 $M_{univ} = 6.18 \pm 0.95$; mean value for the cinema $M_{cin} = 5.70 \pm 1.33$; scale from 1 ('not at
 262 all') to 7 ('enjoyed it a lot')). They were entertained (rating ≥ 5 ; university: 83%, cinema:
 263 63%) and showed high interest (rating ≥ 5 : university: 92%, cinema: 81%) (Table 1).

264

265 The focus group session reinforced findings that the S&C format is able to link
 266 entertainment and scientific information (see also Table 2 and [S4](#), pos. 265). The event
 267 evoked various alternating emotions, sparked interest, and linked positive feelings with
 268 the acquisition of knowledge (pos. 276-278, 369, 488-492).

269
270

Table 1: Fulfilment of expectations through the event, grouped by event locations university (n=62) and cinema (n=33). Rating scale from 1 (not at all) to 7 (fully met).

Expectations met for ...	Setting	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
entertainment	university	5.81	1.3	2	7
	cinema	5.00	1.46	1	7
interest	university	6.16	0.94	4	7
	cinema	5.64	1.39	2	7
scientific information	university	5.95	1.09	3	7
	cinema	5.52	1.48	2	7

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Table 2: Summary of the focus group discussion.

Code	Summary	Illustrative quotes
Perception of the S&C event	<p>Expectations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entertainment (Pos. 159; 401-402); - scientific climate facts (Pos. 159); - reflection by the scientist (Pos. 160; 395) <p>Perception of event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - positive: entertaining, interesting; 'reality check' (Pos. 157-160); combination of entertaining, emotional clips with scientific information (Pos. 265; 274; 488-492) - more accessible than classical talks; movies as means for identification (Pos. 266-267; 273) - impetus to (re-)encourage reflection on climate change (Pos. 152; 396) - critical: partly expectations that reflection of film blocks would entail more direct analysis of clips (Pos. 91, Pos. 513); too few new movies for younger audiences (Pos. 246-248) 	<p>"And there I think S&C is actually quite brilliant. Because of the movies. Most people like movies at least a little or even a lot. And watching movies is something emotional that you associate with a lot, something exciting, something funny. And I think using that to communicate scientific content is basically very ingenious." (Pos. 265).</p> <p>"It was fun at first. With <i>Ice Age</i> and stuff: 'Hey, I know that movie!' And then: 'Wow!' Really surprised, and then: 'Okay, that wall really existed. Exciting.' [...] I learned something! And that was a positive feeling for me. In between, it was a bit depressing again when you hear: 'And here we are now. It doesn't look good.' And then you think to yourself: 'We did well!' [ironically]. And then <i>The March</i> was... You feel helpless." (Pos. 276)</p>

Code	Summary	Illustrative quotes
Perception of climate change	<p>Knowledge and understanding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gained insight in scientific facts on climate change (Pos. 91; 159); partly new knowledge (Pos.46-49; 221; 276; 314-315; 491) - more differentiated perception and nuanced emotional response due to the scientist's reflection; reassurance (Pos. 222) <p>Emotions and motivation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - clips of <i>The March</i> lead to feelings of helplessness (Pos. 109-110; 276; 368), but also to looking from different angles, like climate justice and social justice. (Pos. 132-133) <p>Risk perception:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - risk perception was intensified when clips were connected with real life events; e.g., for <i>The March</i> in connection with the migration wave in 2015 (Pos. 132) or for <i>Soylent Green</i> (the last trees in New York; paper as rarity) referencing to recent forest diebacks (Pos. 309). - Fostered perception of urgency to act against climate change (Pos. 312-313; 368; 379; 385) 	<p>"Before the event, [...] my general attitude toward climate change, was that it's very serious, that we should be afraid, and that we absolutely must do something about it. And I expected the event to reinforce that view. But the reality today is a bit more nuanced. [...] And in some respects, it has almost reassured me a little. Not in the sense that nothing needs to be done now, but rather in the sense that we can still achieve it." (Pos. 222)</p> <p>"But the movie [<i>The March</i>] really addressed a completely different level, namely the refugee issue. And for me, it actually triggered a lot of memories of 2015. [...] And I think that people in our age group are familiar with these photos and this issue, and maybe some people were motivated to look at it from a different perspective. That climate justice and social justice simply go hand in hand." (Pos. 132)</p>
Reflection, meaning-making	<p>Realism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participants saw the risk of confounding fiction with realism higher for narratives set in the future or representations being closer to documentaries (Pos. 37-38; 45; 67-68; 74) - Person 4 remembered that while watching the movie <i>The Day After Tomorrow</i> as a child, he found this devastating being a possible future scenario (Pos. 76) <p>Reflection, meaning-making:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participants saw the main purpose of the event as stimulating reflection (Pos. 152; 369-377; 390-396); they partly picked up discussion with friends or family after the event (Pos. 136; 369) - participants referenced to local events or developments, like migration crisis in 2015 (Pos. 136) or tree dying because of drought (Pos. 309), underlining their importance for reflection beyond movies 	<p>"But I do believe that people draw conclusions from movies. So, if you set the film in 2030 and say: Yes, there is a bit of climate change and you see some extreme events shown in the movie or something like that. Then people might think: "Okay, maybe that's real." or "Maybe that's well researched." And that's now... "That's how it will really happen." (Person 3; pos. 45)</p> <p>"Yes, the scene with those last trees in Manhattan, for example [...]. That really upset me because I thought to myself: The movie is, I don't know, from the 80s or something. And back then, people still imagined that as a distant future, but nowadays in Germany we're actually already facing the problem that certain tree species simply can't survive anymore and fall down in rows. (Pos. 309)</p>

275 Scientific information

276 In both settings, most participants felt informed by the event (rating ≥ 5 : university: 87%,
 277 cinema: 78%) (Table 1). In a self-referential question whether one feels to know more
 278 about climate change than before the event, 54% for the university event ($M = 4.35 \pm$
 279 1.66) and 48% for the cinema ($M = 4.24 \pm 1.56$) rated 5 or higher on a scale from 1
 280 ('familiar with all of this') to 7 ('very new to me') (see Figure 4).
 281

282

283 **Figure 4:** The participants' feeling of gaining more knowledge about climate change through the
 284 event.

285

286 When asking if the scientist was able to contribute towards changing their attitudes
 287 regarding climate change (Table 3), participants partially agreed to better
 288 understanding (rating ≥ 5 : university: 42%, cinema: 60%) and to gaining more
 289 knowledge (rating ≥ 5 : university: 64%, cinema: 72%), with slightly higher ratings in the
 290 cinema setting.

291

292 **Table 3:** Changes in the view on climate change by self-referential ratings, grouped by event
 293 locations. Rating scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree).

View on climate change	Setting	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
better insight / better understanding	university	4.02	1.61	1	7
	cinema	4.58	1.73	1	7
more knowledge	university	4.92	1.46	2	7
	cinema	5.33	1.57	2	7
higher risk perception	university	3.82	1.63	1	7

	cinema	3.85	1.70	1	7
greater sense of concern	university	3.98	1.63	1	7
	cinema	3.85	1.79	1	7
more worried	university	3.47	1.67	1	7
	cinema	3.45	1.60	1	7
more motivated	university	4.74	1.41	1	7
	cinema	4.27	1.51	1	7

294

295 *Motivation and concern*

296 In pre-post comparison, participants' general concern for climate change remained
 297 stable at a high level (item *climate_worry_a*, pre: $M = 5.81 \pm 1.29$, post: $M = 5.54 \pm$
 298 1.28). However, participants partially agreed that the scientist changed their view on
 299 climate change in terms of higher risk perception, greater sense of concern, and more
 300 motivation (mean values between 3.45 and 4.74; Table 3). 66% of participants at
 301 university and 51% at the cinema were generally motivated by the event to do more to
 302 combat climate change (rating ≥ 5).

303

304 Participants of the focus group did not see the primary purpose of the format as being
 305 to motivate, but instead to gain insights from the expert, stimulate reflection, and to
 306 refresh awareness for the topic (pos. 152; 369-377; 390-396). However, they reported
 307 that the event had strengthened their already climate-friendly attitude (pos. 3, 109-110,
 308 222).

309 *The scientist's perspective*

310 The scientist perceives the S&C format as a refreshingly new approach compared to
 311 talks and lectures. This could reach people who may not feel addressed by traditional
 312 presentations. He points out: "*I actually only see advantages here. Of course,*
 313 *entertainment films are not documentaries, and the depictions are correspondingly*
 314 *dramatic – but the accompanying discussions offer precisely the opportunity to clear*
 315 *this up.*" His aim is to raise awareness of the urgency to act against climate change
 316 without causing a feeling of hopelessness.

317 **Discussion**

318 Representations of scientific topics in popular culture influence our perceptions about
 319 science (Bucchi & Trench, 2021; Davies et al., 2019; Sakellari 2015). Film-makers use
 320 movies as instrument to challenge our understanding of reality or to shape speculative
 321 futures, thereby popularizing scientific concepts (Felgueiras & Ruão, 2025). They do
 322 not only spark the audience's interest in scientific topics (Hart & Leiserowitz, 2009), but
 323 also "influence people's belief structures significantly by shaping, cultivating or
 324 reinforcing the cultural meanings of science" (Kirby, 2008, p. 41). Movies also reinforce
 325 societal views by repeating cultural stereotypes, like the heroic scientist unheard by

326 politics (Felgueiras, 2025; Kirby, 2008). For *The Day after Tomorrow*, reception studies
327 have shown changes in concern about climate change or a reduced belief in the
328 likelihood of extreme events as impact of climate change (Lowe et al., 2006; Kirby,
329 2008). With S&C, we provide a science communication format that uses these
330 cinematic representations to connect to actual conceptions and societal discourse. The
331 S&C format offers potential for science communication in several ways: (1) It examines
332 popular conceptions and stimulates the audience to reflect on them; (2) it engages the
333 audience through entertainment and emotion; and (3) it appeals to different target
334 groups.

335
336 The results of this study show the format's potential to provide thematical insight and
337 to improve scientific understanding. Although data revealed only modest changes for
338 motivation, risk perception and concern, the discussion in the focus group
339 demonstrated that the images transported in the clips provoked reflection. Several
340 studies have shown that viewers of cli-fi films are uncertain when to distinguish factual
341 science from imaginary fiction (Busselle & Bilandzic, 2008; Griffin, 2017; Lowe et al.,
342 2006). In S&C, the scientist takes advantage of the audience's attentive state to
343 debunk misrepresentations and clarify scientific background which may help the
344 audience to gain a more differentiated and correct picture. This conclusion is supported
345 by the fact that the focus group members picked up on several images conveyed in
346 the clips (such as the protection of the last tree in New York) and on information
347 provided by the scientist (such as changes in regional precipitation patterns), and
348 linked them to real events of their local environment (the forest dieback in Germany)
349 (Table 2). Movies may not only distort scientific facts, they may also use tropes or
350 stereotypes, like climate dystopia or a hero scientist (Felgueiras & Ruão, 2025). This
351 should be taken into account during clip selection and taken up in moderator-scientist
352 discussion. Future research could examine the effectiveness of S&C in challenging
353 these tropes through explicit reflection or by showing them next to clips of independent
354 films breaking up with inadequate stereotype representations.

355
356 The results of our study suggest that the impressive and moving film clips were able
357 to elicit emotions and affect, which could be verified in further research. Emotions are
358 known to be intertwined with cognition and motivation. For information processing,
359 emotional flow from fear to hope may be especially favorable (Nabi et al., 2018).
360 However, focus group members reported to feel helpless during the block on migration,
361 which hints toward ethical challenges and suggests a prudent use of clips that may
362 foster hopelessness or anxiety.

363
364 Research shows that science events often attract highly educated or science-affiliated
365 individuals, potentially perpetuating exclusivity (DeWitt & Archer, 2017). In our study,
366 the venue significantly impacted who was participating. The cinema as a venue may
367 have felt more open, an aspect that could include people who have no direct
368 connection to university or science (Dawson et al., 2024; DeWitt & Archer, 2017).
369 Although varied with regard to demographics, the audiences of both settings perceived
370 the event as entertaining, interesting, and thought-provoking. This highlights the

371 potential to broaden knowledge and encourage reflection, particularly among non-
372 university affiliates, which emphasizes the value of off-campus events. However, both
373 events attracted audiences who were already engaged in the topic of climate change.
374 In future, S&C could be integrated in public settings, like art festivals or open-air
375 cinema, providing the chance of an unplanned encounter. This kind of “Guerilla
376 Science” (Rosin et al., 2023) blending various elements of access showed potentials
377 to reach non-traditional audiences. Furthermore, S&C episodes can be adapted in
378 content and attractiveness for different target audiences by film choice (genre, age) and
379 clip selection, e.g., adapting it for pupils or highlighting a topic of special interest for a
380 community. The collaboration with interest groups (e.g., cultural centers) may help to
381 adapt the event to the audience’s needs, like engaging an interpreter, providing
382 subtitles or inviting discussants from their community for joint reflection.

383 *Limitations*

384 Insights from our practice report are limited due to the small and imbalanced
385 quantitative data set pointing out tendencies rather than robust significant results.
386 Accuracy of focus group data may be limited by several factors. First, only a small and
387 homogenous sample was obtained (N=5, all young and highly educated), which limited
388 the breadth of insight. Second, accuracy of retrospective data – the discussion took
389 place three days after the event – may be distorted, e.g., due to omission like forgetting,
390 emotion in memory retrieval, or motivation-related bias by a need for self-enhancement
391 or social desirability (Müggenburg, 2021). Third, the focus group took place only after
392 the university event, so that comparisons with perspectives of the cinema’s audience
393 are missing.

394

395 The role of the scientist entails high thematic and interpretative power, which may limit
396 reflective insights and may provide opportunity to pursue an own agenda
397 (implementation intentions; Gollwitzer & Sheeran, 2006). With regard to the framework
398 for social conversation around science by Bucchi and Trench (2021), the S&C has
399 elements of a rather closed model for science communication: together with the S&C
400 team the scientist decides on the main scientific aspects and the film clips to be
401 included and he enacts a rather authoritative role while interpreting and correcting the
402 conveyed images and imparting scientific knowledge. However, there are also
403 elements of dialogue and participation. The film clips themselves provide a cultural
404 perspective on the topic. Furthermore, it is the moderator who takes on the role of the
405 lay audience, asking critical questions and contributing popular viewpoints on the
406 topics under discussion, thereby creating a kind of vicarious dialogue in interpretation
407 and (re-)construction of knowledge. At the end of the event, the audience is
408 encouraged to join the discussion by sharing their thoughts, asking questions and
409 expressing concerns, thereby starting a process of joint meaning-making. To further
410 develop the S&C concept, measures to balance the authority of the scientist could be
411 taken, e.g., by including another expert in clip selection and reflection or by increasing
412 the time for final discussion with the audience.

413

414 *Recommendations*

415 Based on the evaluation, we make the following recommendations:

- 416 • Maintain a balance between entertaining stories and scientific insights, and
417 correct misrepresentations. Given that S&C audiences expected scientific
418 insights and entertainment rather than detailed research results, we recommend
419 focusing on general understanding of scientific concepts.
- 420 • Incorporate references to local environments to enhance the connection of
421 scientific topics to the self and community, which showed high resonance in our
422 focus group discussion (e.g., forest dieback, Table 2).
- 423 • Utilize film narratives to establish a connection with the audience and evoke an
424 emotional response. When utilizing emotion-based messaging, make prudent
425 use of clips eliciting negative emotions like fear and combine them with
426 messages of hope and solutions to promote emotional flow and mitigate
427 maladaptive effects (Dennison, 2024; Nabi et al., 2018).

428

429 Based on the lessons learned from implementation, we make the following practical
430 recommendations:

- 431 • Select event venues and frameworks according to the target audience. Our
432 results underline the importance of off-campus events to facilitate access for
433 people from diverse backgrounds.
- 434 • Reach out to facilitators within the community of your target audience to
435 advertise the event or to participate as a discussant. Our results showed that
436 most people engage due to personal contacts.
- 437 • Make sure to apply for film screening licenses while preparing your event.

438 **Conclusions**

439 Our perception of science and scientific topics is not only shaped by traditional science
440 communication itself, but also by the cultural conversation around science as a whole,
441 including images and representations conveyed in the media and our popular culture.
442 Taking these into account may guide new approaches in science communication
443 practice, since we can make them explicit, examine them, and encourage critical
444 reflection. This seems especially relevant in times of information overload and
445 increasing presence of false or misleading statements. The findings from our
446 evaluation suggest that the S&C format presented here is able to make the audience
447 question these images and to clarify the scientific perspective on the topic at hand.
448 Further, it is able to attract interest of both people with higher and lower formal affinity
449 levels to science. We argue that especially for scientific topics that are strongly present
450 in societal discourses, S&C can contribute to our understanding, reflection, and
451 development of cultural conceptions of science.

452

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559 **Open Science and Ethics Statement**

560 This study was approved by the local University of [anonymized] Ethics Committee
561 (No. 2022/23/56). Informed consent to participate was obtained from all participants.
562 Data and materials are available at the Open Science Framework repository
563 (https://osf.io/ahytv/?view_only=aab00304f900477cae9c3ce0b667ab3d).

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